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SECTION 16.

HISTORY, ARCHEOLOGY AND CULTUROLOGY

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SOME OBSERVATIONS ON THE HISTORY OF KHOREZM IN MIDDLE PERSIAN (PAHLAVI) SOURCES

Although the Afrighid dynasty's reign(305-995 AD) holds a significant place in the history of Uzbek statehood, its study is fraught with challenges. The scarcity of available written sources and the contradictions within their information pose serious problems for researchers. To overcome these obstacles and achieve a comprehensive understanding of the Afrighid dynasty's history, a multifaceted approach is essential [10]. It is imperative to expand research beyond traditional Arabic and Persian sources to include Chinese, Pahlavi, Armenian, and Syriac texts. Identifying and analyzing previously unexplored information that has not yet entered scholarly discourse is also crucial. By comparing and conducting comparative analyses of data from diverse sources, we can assess their reliability and reconstruct a more accurate picture of historical events. Only through such a comprehensive approach can we achieve a holistic and unbiased study of the Afrighid dynasty's history and properly evaluate their contribution to the development of Uzbek statehood.

Analyses indicate that the study of Khorezm`s history based on Pahlavi sources remains an open question in both foreign and national historiography. While foreign scholars have incorporated some information from Pahlavi sources in their studies of Iranian history, Uzbek historiography has largely neglected these resources.

Middle Persian sources encompass a wealth of information on the social, political, religious, philosophical, literary, and other aspects of life in the Sasanian Empire (224-651 CE) and its neighboring regions. However, from a historiographical perspective, it is crucial to acknowledge their unique characteristics and limitations. As Iranian scholar T. Daryaee points out, the majority of Pahlavi sources were written and copied by Zoroastrian priests. Their primary objective was not to record events in chronological order, but rather to

preserve sacred traditions [2]. Furthermore, due to the cosmological and eschatological perspectives embedded in Middle Persian literature, these texts often prioritize mythical and religious elements over precise historical details.

Scholar G. Widengren notes that among Pahlavi sources, the "Bundahishn" ("Original Creation") and the "Karnamag-i Ardashir-i Pabagan" ("Book of the Deeds of Ardashir") present historical events in chronological order [9]. The "Bundahishn" offers cosmological and geographical information about Khwarezm, notably mentioning it as one of the important regions created by Ahura Mazda. It also highlights Khwarezm's well-irrigated lands, fertile soil, and the agricultural and pastoral activities of its inhabitants [8]. The latter source is a blend of legendary and historical narratives from the Sasanian era. Its unique feature is its inclusion of various details about titles and positions established towards the end of the Sasanian period. However, scholar R.N. Frye points out that the claim in this source about Sogdiana and Khwarezm being ruled by the Sasanian king Ardashir is not corroborated by any other sources [3].

Another crucial source illuminating the political relations between Sasanian Iran and Khwarezm is the "Paikuli Inscription," located near the village of Barkal in Iraq's Sulaymaniyah Governorate. This inscription commemorates the victory of the Sasanian emperor Narseh over his nephew Bahram III and details the reasons for his deposition. It also lists rulers who supported Narseh or submitted to the Sasanian Empire after his ascension to the throne [6]. The mention of the King of Khwarezm among them serves as compelling evidence of the Sasanian Empire's political and military influence in Central Asia, particularly in Khwarezm.

The discovery and study of the "Paikuli Inscription" spanned many years and involved the efforts of several renowned scholars. In 1844, the British orientalist Henry Rawlinson first discovered the monument. Subsequently, German orientalist Ernst Herzfeld visited the site in 1911, 1913, and 1923, undertaking the task of reading and transcribing the inscriptions. In 1954, researchers from Iraq's "Ancient Objects and Cultural Heritage" committee conducted further investigations at the site. By 2007, Italian archaeologist Gianfilippo Terribili, in collaboration with archaeologists in Sulaymaniyah, successfully transferred over 120 stone slabs to the Sulaymaniyah Museum and deciphered their inscriptions [4].

Foreign historians, including R.N. Frye, T. Daryaee, R. Shayegan, J. Pickett, S. Malekzadeh, and N. Nematollahi, have extensively utilized the information from the "Paikuli Inscription" in their studies of the political relations between Iran and Khwarezm during the early medieval period.

The "Letter of Tansar" is yet another vital source shedding light on the political dynamics between the Sasanians and Khwarezm. This 6th-century Sasanian

propaganda tool not only addresses the relationship between religion and state but also provides valuable information on the system of cities and districts, as well as political, military, and civil administration. The letter, serving the Sasanian state's political agenda, portrays the Arsacid era as a time of moral corruption and beliefs contrary to Zoroastrianism, thereby justifying the Sasanian rise to power and legitimizing their rule. Furthermore, it promotes the idea of unity between the Zoroastrian church and the Iranian state. The historical significance of the "Letter of Tansar" lies in its overt manipulation of history to serve Sasanian political goals and legitimize their rule. Through this document, the Sasanians sought to consolidate their authority, discredit the previous dynasty, and emphasize the intrinsic connection between religion and state [1].

The "Letter of Tansar" was translated into Arabic in the 9th century by Ibn al-Muqaffa and later into New Persian in the 13th century by Ibn Isfandiyar, who incorporated it into his "History of Tabaristan." Currently, neither the original Middle Persian version nor the Arabic translation is extant [5]. The letter was first published in 1894 by the French orientalist James Darmesteter, based on two manuscripts of the "History of Tabaristan" [4]. In 1926, Iranian scholar Ali-Akbar Dehkhoda published the "Letter of Tansar" with explanations and annotations. German and English translations followed in 1965 and 1968, respectively [7].

Scholars such as R.N. Frye, V.G. Lukonin, T. Daryaei, and R. Shayegan have relied on translations of this letter to elucidate the political relationship between the Sasanians and Khwarezm.

A particularly noteworthy aspect of the letter is the Sasanian king's practice of bestowing the title of "MLK" exclusively upon members of the royal family and border rulers. The ruler of Khwarezm is mentioned among those who received this title, alongside Alans, western governors, and rulers of Kabul [5]. This information suggests two possibilities. Firstly, the Sasanian Empire may have pursued a policy of forming alliances and granting certain privileges to local rulers to strengthen its influence in border regions. The title of "MLK" could have been one such privilege. Secondly, it is possible that a local dynasty closely aligned with the Sasanian Empire ruled Khwarezm. This dynasty might have partially adopted the Sasanian political system and supported mutually beneficial relations.

In conclusion, Middle Persian sources represent a unique and invaluable resource for studying the complex political relationship between the Sasanian Empire and Khwarezm. However, their specific characteristics, including their creation under the influence of particular ideologies and occasional contradictions with other sources, necessitate a cautious and critical approach in their utilization.

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